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STUDENT BEHAVIOUR AND LEARNING OUTCOMES IN A FLIPPED CLASSROOM WITH ON-DEMAND LECTURES AND ONLINE PEER TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

To create opportunities for collaboration among students and to improve learning outcomes during the COVID-19 pandemic, we designed a flipped classroom that combined on-demand lectures and simultaneous interactive online classes with peer teaching. We assessed the relationship between student behaviour and learning outcomes. The results showed that the students who achieved higher grades were more active and autonomous learners than their counterparts with lower grades, in both on-demand lectures and peer teaching.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Flipped Classroom

Flipped classroom is an instructional strategy where students are provided with a set of preparation tasks prior to participating in more socially active and engaging face-to-face lessons [1]. Mason [2] pointed out the effectiveness of the flipped classroom in comparison to the traditional classroom in terms of content coverage, student performance and student observations and perceptions of the flipped classroom format. Overall, the flipped classroom is effective reliant on the level of student engagement with the preparatory activities prior to attending the face-to-face teaching sessions [3].

1.2 Fully Online Flipped Classroom During the COVID-19 Pandemic

If faculty members deliver one-way online lectures to a large class, students may have difficulty staying focused and can become demotivated. Moreover, students who are isolated within the context of the COVID-19 pandemic are deprived of the opportunity to learn from each other. To solve this problem, a fully online flipped class was designed to strengthen students' independent learning and concentration as well as to promote their collaboration and mutual learning. The flipped classroom combined on-demand lectures and simultaneous interactive online classes with peer teaching [4]. It was applied in 'Systems Engineering', a course offered through the College of Systems Engineering and Science. Approximately 600 students from five departments enrolled, and four faculty

members taught the classes. The face-to-face lessons were held in four large classrooms for 160 students each.

1.3 Aim of the Study

This study investigates the relationship between students' behaviour related to preparing for class and their learning outcomes in the flipped classroom with on-demand lectures and online peer teaching.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Procedure

We designed a combination of on-demand and simultaneous bi-directional classes, as shown in Figure 1, and followed the procedure shown in Figure 2. In the fully online flipped classroom, students acquired knowledge through on-demand lectures and studied the subject matter before attending a simultaneous interactive online class. During the class, they were divided into small groups for peer teaching. This allowed them to learn independently and actively and to freely communicate with each other.

Fig. 1. Configuration of the fully online flipped class with peer teaching.

Fig. 2. Weekly schedule

The students were instructed to read designated sections of the textbook, review the assignments and watch the necessary parts of the on-demand lectures before the interactive class. They also submitted weekly assignments. They submitted a tentative assignment on the morning of the class and a final assignment two days after the class. The tentative submission served as evidence that the students had prepared for the class and did not require correct answers.

The 100-minute interactive class began with 20 minutes of instruction, followed by 60 minutes of peer teaching in 43 breakout sessions of four students each. The students then returned to the plenary session for 20 minutes of questions and answers. They were required to finish the final submission within two days of the class session.

2.2 Questionnaire

A questionnaire survey was administered to 176 students in one of the four classes. The students completed the questionnaire after the class. It contained a total of seven items: five questions about their class preparation behaviour and the benefits of peer teaching,

and two questions about whether they preferred flipped classroom teaching or traditional classroom teaching and which format they preferred peer teaching to take place in.

Questionnaire:

I would like to ask you about your preparation for class. Please answer the following questions.

- (1) How many minutes did you spend reading the textbook or other materials to prepare for each class?
- (2) How many minutes did you spend watching the class recording to prepare for one class?
- (3) How many minutes did you spend on the assignment to prepare for one class?
- (4) Have you been actively involved in peer teaching?
- (5) Has peer teaching been useful to you?
- (6) Which do you prefer, a flipped classroom or traditional classroom?
- (7) Which is the best way to implement peer teaching—in an online class, in a face-to-face class, or switching between online and face-to-face classes on a weekly basis?

2.3 Analysis

A correlation analysis was conducted on the responses of 128 students (out of the 176 students in the class) for whom both the questionnaire responses and grades were valid. Then, the data of 28 students (of the 128 students) with intermediate grades were excluded, and a comparison of student behaviour was made between the top 50 and bottom 50 students.

3 RESULTS

Table 1 shows the relationship between the students' class preparation and their grades. Compared to students with lower grades, the students who achieved higher grades spent more time reading the textbook (Question 1) and examining assignments as preparation (Question 3) ($p < 0.05$). On the other hand, there was no significant difference in the amount of time spent watching on-demand lectures (Question 2). There was a significant difference ($p < 0.01$) in the total amount of time spent preparing for each class, with the top performers spending an average of 192.4 minutes and the bottom performers spending an average of 153.4 minutes.

Table 2 shows the relationship between the students' behaviour in peer teaching and their grades. Both the high- and low-achieving students actively participated in peer teaching, but the high-achieving students engaged more actively ($p < 0.05$). There was no significant difference between the two groups in terms of the effectiveness of peer teaching. In the open-ended responses, the high-achieving students said that peer teaching helped them get answers to their questions and that they understood more by teaching colleagues. The low-achieving students only wrote that peer teaching answered their questions.

In response to the question about their preference for a flipped or traditional classroom, 60% of the high-achieving students and 36% of the low-achieving students chose the flipped classroom, while 22% of the high-achieving students and 30% of the low-achieving students

chose the traditional classroom. The rest responded that they had an equal preference for the two approaches. As for the format of peer teaching, 52% of the top-performing students and 56% of the bottom-performing students reported that they preferred it to take place online, while 26% of the top-performing students and 28% of the bottom-performing students preferred a face-to-face approach. The remaining students said they would like alternating online and face-to-face weeks.

Table 1. Relationship between students' class preparation and grades

	Question (Answer in minutes)	Students with higher grades		Students with lower grades		p-value	
		(n = 50)		(n = 50)			
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
1	How many minutes did you spend reading the textbook or other materials to prepare for each class?	56.1	36.7	43.4	22.8	0.020	*
2	How many minutes did you spend watching the class recording to prepare for one class?	34.6	28.6	32.0	25.7	0.318	
3	How many minutes did you spend on the assignment to prepare for one class?	101.7	61.6	78.0	38.4	0.012	*
	Total	192.4	89.6	153.4	64.9	0.007	**

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$

Table 2. Relationship between students' behaviour in peer teaching and grades

	Question	Answer		Students with higher grades		Students with lower grades		p-value	
				(n = 50)		(n = 50)			
4	Have you been actively involved in peer teaching?	active	5	56.0%	90.0%	30.0%	80.0%	0.010	**
		somewhat active	4	34.0%		50.0%			
		neither active nor passive	3	6.0%	6.0%	14.0%	14.0%		
		somewhat passive	2	4.0%	4.0%	6.0%	6.0%		
		passive	1	0.0%		0.0%			
5	Has peer teaching been useful to you?	useful	5	44.0%	82.0%	42.00%	70.0%	0.38	
		somewhat useful	4	38.0%		28.00%			
		neither useful nor unuseful	3	6.0%	6.0%	24.00%	24.0%		
		somewhat unuseful	2	10.0%	12.0%	6.00%	6.0%		
		not useful	1	2.0%		0.00%			

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$

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